

THE ROLE OF USING INTERACTIVE SOFTWARE TOOLS IN THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCIES OF ELEMENTARY STUDENTS

Davranova Gulbahor Numondjonovna

Basic doctoral student of Bukhara Institute of Engineering Technology

(sunny.davranova@gmail.com)

Abstract: This article describes the ideas that the emergence of multimedia and information technology has opened a wide path to the use of public education schools as an effective tool in educational and educational, communication processes, the development of a harmonious personality of information technology, its independent choice of profession and an increasing role and influence on self-formation, professional development.

Key words: primary class, information technology, multimedia, software tools, training, professional skills, computer, text editor, information resources, interactive lessons.

In keeping with the period, the application of information technology to the educational process of secondary schools, which is rapidly expanding into the practice of all spheres, day after day, has become one of the pressing issues. Nowadays, education is difficult to imagine without Information Communication Technologies. Personal computers are the main technical means of computer education technology. Today, in the educational process, it is also advisable to use tablets, electronic whiteboards, smartphones, smart TVs that work on the android system. They are required for the purpose of effective use in the educational processes of primary classes- software tools, e – books, computer games, internet network, slides, presentations, animated video rollers, etc. Educational materials in the content of innovative software tools should be based on a dynamic nature and consist of animations of changing, developing and complex character as a result of the historical process, and sound, moving States.

Traditional visual weapons, which have been used in the educational system for a long time, are static in nature, with one or two characteristics and do not change during the entire historical process. For example, when introducing wild animals in a foreign language session, a teacher shows cards with wild animal figures on cardboard in the traditional way (static tool). And in the training organized through software tools, through a video roller depicting the true appearance of wild animals, it is introduced to its movements, sound, living addresses, diet, gangs, hunting processes (dynamic tool). As a result, the content of education, the mechanism of influence of the material on the student's consciousness is increased several times and it is achieved that it is stored in the student's memory for a long time and realizes phenomena and processes within the framework of real thinking.

Currently, the creation of various software tools designed for students of primary school age is rapidly developing. Innovative educational software tools used in primary classes can be divided into two groups:

1. Software tools provided through a 3D environment designed to teach and educate, to understand values (electronic textbook, electronic training development based on innovative artificial intelligence, trips through a computerized 3D environment, illustrated-annotated cartoons, fairy tales featuring educational values, mathematical fairy tales, etc.);

2. Visual media (collection of electronic images, slides, presentations, tables, graphs, photographs, etc.

Innovative software tools prepared for elementary students are required to be voice, musical, action, animated, multiplicative, engaging, and interactive. Because the retention of information received through vision, hearing, perception in memory of up to 75% has been determined during studies.

In recent years, the development of software tools has been established in our Republic, which are widely used for use in the educational process. In particular, many software tools are produced by the Center for the development of multimedia

general education programs. For example, in 2015, multimedia software tools in the form of an application to educational textbooks of Russian, reading, mathematics, English and native language were provided for 1st graders and in the educational process showed an effective result in mastering subjects with great interest in 1st graders.

The second source is internet tools. Various types of video, music, painting, animation, cartoon, fairy tale, video film, multimedia tools, computer games, and other types of material are posted on Internet web pages. Their effective use serves to improve the quality of Education. The options for the preparation of simple types of multimedia and its use in the training process are presented below.

Usually innovative software tools are divided into two types:

1. Inimatory video rollers, video Films, educational and educational cartoons and fairy tales, developed on the basis of visual-image, analog, roller-plot educational methods. These products are made in various animator programs, video editors. For example, *Macromedia Flash, an Animator, scratch, Power Point, Video animator, Camtasia Studio, Crazy Talk Animator*, etc.

2. Computer games developed on the basis of the reproductive, productive, zinama-zina and dialaog techniques, while the assignment system is developed mainly through programming languages. For example, programs such as *C++*, *C#*, *Action Script*, *Pyton* are prepared in languages. It is also possible to prepare the simplest computer games through hypersiles in the Power Point program.

The totality of materials belonging to these two types forms an excellent source of training. Because video rollers are used in the topic introduction part of the training, and the assignment system is used in the reinforcement part.

Today, various teaching software tools are widely used in the educational systems of developed countries of the world. Instructional visual software tools are created using authoring software. The use of such programs in the educational process is high-performing, the reason is that when receiving information regarding

the knowledge transmitted in the audience and performing tasks, the student simultaneously hears and sees and assimilates.

Author software is a software tool designed to partially or completely automate the learning process using computer technology. They are considered one of the promising forms of improving the effectiveness of the educational process and are used as a teaching tool of modern technologies. It is very convenient to create electronic textbooks using author's software. Electronic textbooks, using computer technology, maximize understanding of the most important concepts and laws as well as keeping in mind. Below is an overview of the capabilities of author's software.

Examples of authoring programs include *Articulate Storyline*, *Adobe Captivate*, *CourseLab*, *iSpringPro*, *Lectora*, *Camtasia Studio*, *Ulead Gif Animator program*.

In addition, it is possible to convert a file prepared in a simple Word editor into a graphic file, convert graphic files of one format into graphic files of another format, concentrate several multimedia applications into single multimedia applications, implement multimedia applications in size, size, quality and structure through multimedia applications. Such applications include *Adobe PageMaker*, *Adobe Photoshop*, *Adobe Flash*, *3d Max*.

The most commonly used modern foreign-language computer programs developed in the United States, such as *Wordstock*, *Matchmaster*, *Choicemaster*, *Crosswordmaster*, *Gapmaster*, etc. These programs reveal the features of language teaching working with vocabulary, matching lexical units, creating multiple choice exercises, and working with texts such as *Gapmaster*, *Pinpoint*, and *Speedread*.

Hence, multimedia tools have a great role in organizing the educational process at school. A distinctive feature of multimedia is a high information density and a complete set of the most effective educational components-a synthesis of text, visualization and audio materials that allow multimodal perception of information with the activation of several information channels.

Thus, the use of Information Technology in classes gives a lasting result, primarily due to the use of the creative potential of students, which leads to the formation of a state of success and increases motivation in teaching. The effectiveness of the lesson is achieved due to the optimal combination of innovative tools and teaching methods that maximize cognitive activity, the desire to solve problem situations and the independence of students. Therefore, information and computer technology is a means of activating creative potential and improving the quality of knowledge in the study of a foreign language.

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